

A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW ON SUPPORTIVE CARE AND ANTIVIRAL INTERVENTIONS IN PRIMARY HERPETIC GINGIVOSTOMATITIS

F. Kh. Yakubova¹

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute¹

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15086683>

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the study of a review of literary sources of antiviral interventions in primary herpetic gingivostomatosis.*

Keywords: *primary herpetic gingivostomatitis, meningitis, encephalitis, immunocompromised individuals, dehydration.*

Relevance. Herpes viruses, members of the Herpesviridae family, are double-stranded DNA viruses with a distinct four-layered structure comprising a core housing a large, double-stranded DNA genome, an icosahedral capsid, an amorphous protein coat called the tegument, and a lipid bilayer envelope bearing glycoproteins [1,2]. There are over 200 members in this family, and eight of them, including herpes simplex virus (HSV) 1 and 2, varicella-zoster virus (VZV), Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), cytomegalovirus (CMV), human herpesvirus 6 (HHV-6), human herpesvirus 7 (HHV-7), and Kaposi's sarcoma virus (KSHV), are capable of infecting humans [2,6,7].

Herpesviruses are known for infecting various cell types, establishing a reactivatable latent infection in a specific tissue or cell type. Periodically, the virus reactivates, leading to clinical recurrence of the disease, triggered by factors such as heat, cold, trauma, fever, stress, and changes in the host's immune defense status [1,2,3].

HSV-1 is a prominent pathogen responsible for global infections, transmitted through direct contact with lesions or biological fluids like saliva and genital fluids. The majority of people come into contact with HSV-1 in their lifetime, harboring the virus in a latent form. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), as of 2016, an estimated 67% of the global population under the age of 50 had HSV-1 infection (oral or genital), with underestimations due to asymptomatic cases [2]. HSV-1 commonly manifests as painful vesicular lesions in the oral and perioral areas, occasionally causing genital manifestations [2,4,5].

Diagnosis of PHGS is primarily clinical, supported by laboratory tests such as serological assays, the Tzanck test, immunofluorescence, and viral culture. Differential diagnosis involves distinguishing PHGS from other ulcerative diseases. Although PHGS is usually self-limiting, it can lead to complications such as erythema multiforme, aseptic meningitis, and encephalitis, particularly in immunocompromised individuals. Severe cases may necessitate hospitalization due to dehydration caused by difficulties in eating and drinking, particularly in children [11].

Given the potential for discomfort and reduced quality of life, various therapeutic approaches for PHGS have been proposed, ranging from supportive care to antiviral treatments like oral acyclovir within the first 72 hours of disease onset. However, the lack of consensus highlights gaps in existing evidence, with only one previous systematic review focusing on the effectiveness of systemic acyclovir for PHGS. This systematic review aims to address this gap by

comprehensively collecting and critically appraising available evidence on therapeutic strategies for managing PHGS

Materials and methods. The systematic review adhered to the guidelines outlined in the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) statement [15]. The study protocol was registered in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO).

Eligibility. The general eligibility criteria for study inclusion were defined using the "PICO" strategy:

"Population": Immunocompetent children and young adults, of any gender, race, or ethnicity, diagnosed with primary herpetic gingivostomatitis. The diagnosis was confirmed through both clinical history and laboratory investigation.

"Intervention": Any systemic, topical, or physical therapy intended for the treatment of primary herpetic gingivostomatitis (the intervention could be a single approach or a combination of interventions).

"Comparison": Placebo, no intervention, or another active intervention.

"Outcomes": (a) Time of healing for oral and extraoral lesions, drooling, eating and drinking difficulties, and fever. (b) Severity of oral lesions, measured by changes in the number of lesions from the time of intervention administration. (c) Eating and drinking ability. (d) Pain, assessed using a validated pain scale. (e) Viral shedding. (f) HSV quantification. (g) Evaluation of biomarkers.

Inclusion criteria. Eligible studies included randomized trials evaluating the impact of any therapeutic approach for treating primary herpetic gingivostomatitis (PHGS), along with non-randomized intervention studies, controlled before-after studies, and observational studies such as prospective and retrospective cohort studies, case-control studies, and cross-sectional studies.

Exclusion criteria. Exclusion criteria comprised letter to editors, case reports or case series, systematic reviews, duplicate studies, studies not reporting results after the conclusion of the research, preclinical studies, papers presented at scientific events, and articles lacking original data.

Search strategy. The conclusive search was conducted on February 1, 2022, encompassing the following electronic databases—PubMed, Embase, and Scopus—without imposing any date restrictions. The search terms employed were “herpetic gingivostomatitis,” “therapy,” “treatment,” and “management.” These selected terms were amalgamated using Boolean operators in the electronic search: “herpetic gingivostomatitis” AND “therapy”; “herpetic gingivostomatitis” AND “treatment”; and “herpetic gingivostomatitis” AND “management.”

Study selection. Publications in the English language or those with an English language translation were included in the analysis. Duplicate articles were eliminated, and the bibliographies of relevant reviews were manually scrutinized for additional references. Two independent reviewers (TC and NC) conducted screening of titles and abstracts resulting from the initial electronic searches.

Full copies of all studies deemed relevant or potentially relevant, meeting the inclusion criteria, or lacking sufficient data in the title and abstract for a clear decision, underwent further assessment. TC and NC independently evaluated the full-text papers, with any disagreements on the eligibility of included studies resolved through discussion and consensus or, if necessary, adjudicated by a third reviewer (SL) acting as an arbiter.

Irrelevant records were excluded, and the reasons for exclusion were documented. The entire screening and selection process has been delineated in a PRISMA flowchart (Fig. 1).

Data extraction. At least two out of the three reviewers (TC,NC,SL) independently conducted data extraction using a predefined and standardized extraction form. Agreement between the authors was assessed through Cohen’s kappa value (K-statistic: 0.447; standard error: 0.133). The extracted data encompassed general characteristics of the articles (study design, publication year, authors, geographic location) and variables related to study methodology, population, intervention, comparators, and outcomes.

Any discrepancies in the extracted data were resolved through discussion or, if necessary, by involving a fourth reviewer (AB).

Figure 1.

Assessment of risk of bias and quality of studies. The assessment of the risk of bias for each study was independently conducted in duplicate by two authors (TC and NC or AB). This evaluation utilized either version 2 of the Cochrane risk-of-bias tool (RoB 2), designed for assessing the risk of bias in a single estimate of an intervention effect reported from a randomized trial, or the Cochrane risk-of-bias tool (ROBINS-I), which is employed for evaluating the risk of bias in estimates of the comparative effectiveness of interventions from studies without randomization to allocate units to comparison groups [9,8,15].

Any discrepancies in the risk of bias assessment were resolved through discussion, with the involvement of a third author (SL) if necessary.

Data and statistical analysis. Data extraction from the list of eligible articles involved capturing publication and study characteristics (study design, year published, authors, geographic location), study population characteristics (age, sample size), details about the therapy, duration of follow-ups, and outcomes. Given the infeasibility of conducting a meta-analysis, the research team opted to present a narrative summary of results derived from individual studies.

Results. Study selection. A total of 5 studies, encompassing 364 patients with an average age of 7.6 years, met the criteria for inclusion in the review. The initial search yielded 1195 citations. After accounting for duplicates, 790 unique citations remained. Upon reviewing titles and abstracts, 772 studies were excluded as they did not meet the specified criteria. The full text of the remaining 18 citations underwent a more detailed examination, revealing that 13 studies did not align with the inclusion criteria. Consequently, five studies that met the criteria were included in the systematic review. Further exploration of the references in relevant papers and citation searches did not yield additional studies meeting the inclusion criteria. Additionally, no unpublished relevant studies were obtained.

Given the absence of comparable therapies reported in the included literature, a narrative review was conducted. All the studies included in the review focused on patients experiencing the initial clinical presentation of herpetic gingivostomatitis. Among these, three studies (1, 2, and 3) specifically targeted pediatric subjects aged 8 months to 12 years, while the remaining two studies (4 and 5) included adolescents aged 12 to 18 years.

Notably, all the studies were conducted in hospital or university hospital settings, spanning across five different countries.

Risk of bias in studies. Among the included studies, three (1, 2, and 5) were randomized clinical trials, while two (3 and 4) were retrospective. The overall risk of bias, evaluated using RoB 2, was deemed low for studies 1 and 2, with some concern identified for study 5. Assessment with ROBINS-I revealed a serious and moderate overall risk of bias for studies 3 and 4, respectively (Tables 2 and 3).

Studies included in the review	D 1	D 2	D 3	D 4	D 5	Overall
Study 1	+	+	+	+	+	+
Study 2	+	+	+	+	+	+
Study 3	+	-	+	+	+	-

Judgment:

+ low risk

X high risk

– some concerns

Domains:

D1: bias arising from the randomization process

D2: bias due to deviations from intended intervention

D3: bias due to missing outcome data

D4: bias in measurement of the outcome

D5: bias in selection of the reported result

Studies included in the review	D 1	D 2	D 3	D 4	D 5	D 6	D 7	Overall
Study 3	X	-	-	-	X	-	-	X
Study 4	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-

Judgment:

! critical

X serious

- moderate

+ low

? no information

Domains:

D1: bias due to confounding

D2: bias due to selection of participants

D3: bias in classification of interventions

D4: bias due to deviations from intended interventions

D5: bias due to missing data

D6: bias in measurement of outcomes

D7: bias in selection of the reported result

Results of individual studies

Study 1. The group receiving tests (honey plus oral ACV) demonstrated a significantly earlier disappearance of herpetic oral lesions compared to controls (oral ACV) with a median of 3 days versus 6 days ($p = 0.022$). Additionally, notable improvements were observed in drooling (2 days vs. 4 days, $p = 0.030$) and eating difficulty (3 days vs. 8 days, $p = 0.001$). The test group also exhibited significant enhancements in the severity of oral lesions, lower pain scores, improved eating and drinking ability, and a notably reduced need for analgesics at three assessment time-points. Although fever disappeared in both groups, there was no statistically significant difference [16].

Study 2. Children who received acyclovir (ACV) experienced a shorter duration of oral lesions compared to those receiving a placebo, with a median of 4 days versus 10 days (difference of 6 days, 95% confidence interval 4.0 to 8.0). Additionally, the ACV group exhibited an earlier resolution of various signs and symptoms, including fever (1 vs. 3 days, 2 days, 0.8 to 3.2), extraoral lesions (0 vs. 5.5 days, 5.5 days, 1.3 to 4.7), eating difficulties (4 vs. 7 days, 3 days, 1.31 to 4.69), and drinking difficulties (3 vs. 6 days, 3 days, 1.1 to 4.9). Moreover, viral shedding was significantly shorter in the acyclovir-treated group, lasting 1 day compared to 5 days in the placebo group (4 days, 2.9 to 5.1) [11,12,13,14].

Study 3. Topical therapy involving maalox and diphenhydramine or viscous lidocaine was administered to 73% and 15% of the patients, respectively, while acyclovir (ACV) was only

administered to 17% of the cases. The dosing and administration of topical agents for the treatment of primary herpetic gingivostomatitis (PHGS) in preschoolers posed challenges, with ACV being underutilized compared to other topical treatments [15,16,17,18].

Study 4. In assessing the severity of oral lesions, all therapies demonstrated effectiveness, except for mild lesions where no statistically significant improvement was observed in any group (group A: non-alcoholic chlorhexidine (CHX) rinses; group B: non-alcoholic chlorhexidine rinses plus hyaluronic acid gel; group C: non-alcoholic chlorhexidine rinses plus Mucosyte®). For moderate lesions, group C exhibited a significantly larger number of patients with complete healing or improvement compared to group A. No difference was recorded for mild/severe lesions.

Regarding pain scores, a statistically significant difference was observed from T0 to T1 for all groups. Group C showed a significant decrease in pain scores compared to group A. In terms of eating and drinking ability, all patients experienced either total or partial improvement. A significant statistical difference was noted between group A and group C in total and partial recovery, with group C demonstrating full improvement of these abilities [18,19,20].

Study 5. Regarding HSV quantification, a significant reduction was observed in all study groups (group A: topical antiviral therapy (TAT); group B: antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT); group C: combination therapy with TAT + aPDT) during each follow-up. Group C exhibited a statistically higher reduction than both group A and group B. Pain scores significantly decreased in all groups, with Group C reporting a statistically higher decrease compared to both Group A and Group B. In relation to biomarkers, both IL-6 and TNF- α showed a statistically significant reduction after 2 weeks. Group C demonstrated a statistically higher reduction both between groups and within groups at every time point [20].

Results of syntheses. Acyclovir (ACV) was employed either in combination or alone in four of the included studies (1, 2, 3, and 5). In combination, ACV was paired with honey (1), fluids and analgesics (3), and antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT) (5).

When ACV was used alone (study 2), it significantly shortened the duration of all clinical manifestations and the infectivity of affected children compared to placebo.

The combined use of honey and oral ACV (study 1) yielded more favorable outcomes, including the earlier disappearance of herpetic oral lesions, drooling, and eating difficulty; lower pain scores; better eating and drinking ability; and significantly less need for analgesics, compared to acyclovir alone in children with primary herpetic gingivostomatitis (PHGS).

ACV therapy in conjunction with aPDT (study 5) contributed to the reduction of pain scores and pro-inflammatory cytokine levels in herpetic gingivostomatitis among children.

One study (4) utilized non-alcoholic chlorhexidine alone or in combination with other substances, such as hyaluronic acid or verbascoside and sodium hyaluronate (Mucosyte®).

When non-alcoholic chlorhexidine was used in combination with Mucosyte®, a significant improvement in pain scoring and lesion severity was noted compared to non-alcoholic chlorhexidine alone and non-alcoholic chlorhexidine plus hyaluronic acid, respectively.

Study 3 reported the use of fluids and analgesics alone or in combination with viscous lidocaine and a mixture of maalox and diphenhydramine, but the authors did not provide any comparison among the described therapies.

Finally, the studies (4 and 5) that included adolescent patients involved topical therapies and/or non-pharmacological treatments, while the studies (1, 2, and 3) that focused on pediatric subjects primarily employed ACV, except for study 3, which reported mixed therapies.

Outcomes measures. The parameters used to assess the outcomes of therapies varied significantly among the included studies. The most common parameters included eating and drinking abilities/difficulties, severity and duration of oral lesions, pain scores, and fever. Only one study (5) incorporated laboratory tests.

For outcomes common to at least two studies, the summarized results are as follows:

a) Time of healing of oral lesions: 3 days, 4 days, 6 days, and 10 days for ACV plus honey (study 1), ACV suspension (study 2), ACV suspension plus placebo (study 1), and placebo alone (study 2), respectively.

b) Remission of drooling: 2 days, 2 days, 4 days, and 5.5 days for ACV plus honey (study 1), ACV suspension (study 2), ACV suspension plus placebo (study 1), and placebo alone (study 2), respectively.

c) Remission of eating difficulties: 3 days, 4 days, 7 days, and 8 days for ACV plus honey (study 1), ACV suspension (study 2), placebo alone (study 2), and ACV suspension plus placebo (study 1), respectively.

d) Remission of drinking difficulties: 3 days, 3 days, 6 days, and 8 days for ACV plus honey (study 1), ACV suspension (study 2), placebo alone (study 2), and ACV suspension plus placebo (study 1), respectively.

e) Pain scores: A statistically significant reduction was reported for all tests (ACV plus honey; non-alcoholic chlorhexidine rinses plus Mucosyte®; TAT + aPDT) (studies 1, 4, 5) compared to control (ACV plus placebo; non-alcoholic chlorhexidine rinses; TAT) (studies 1, 4, 5).

Finally, the time points for re-evaluation were not consistent among the included studies, but the majority of studies (1, 2, and 4) scheduled the final visit approximately 7 days after the initiation of therapies. One study (3) did not report the time of follow-ups, while one study (5) examined the patients immediately after post-op and then after 2 and 4 weeks, 3 and 6 months.

Discussion. Despite the high incidence and burden of PHGS, this systematic review underscores the limited scientific data available on its treatment. The identified therapeutic approaches in the five included studies encompassed the use of ACV alone or in combination, non-alcoholic chlorhexidine, viscous lidocaine, a mixture of maalox and diphenhydramine, and aPDT. ACV, a well-tolerated antiviral approved in 1982, is considered the first-line treatment for HSV infections, including PHGS. It inhibits viral DNA replication without affecting non-infected cells, and its main side effects include headache, malaise, and vomiting.

The diagnosis of PHGS is challenging due to the absence of a clear cluster arrangement of vesicular lesions, a hallmark of herpes infections, and the rapid resolution of blistering lesions, often resulting in unspecific erosions. The diagnostic delay, often more than 72 hours from onset, may lead to complications such as erythema multiforme, life-threatening encephalitis, dehydration, and ocular involvement. The most common complication is dehydration due to difficulties in eating and drinking, often requiring hospitalization. Erythema multiforme, triggered by HSV-1, is a cell-mediated immune response causing bullae, macules, and papules on the oral mucosa and skin.

ACV has demonstrated efficacy in reducing the duration of oral lesions, fever, and other symptoms if administered within 3 days of onset. However, the studies included in this review mainly focused on symptomatic therapies, such as honey, non-alcoholic chlorhexidine rinses, hyaluronic acid gel, Mucosyte®, or aPDT. These approaches aim to alleviate symptoms, especially

pain, rather than arresting viral replication. Notably, a study comparing topical antiviral therapy, aPDT, and aPDT combined with topical antiviral therapy revealed that the combined approach significantly improved pain scores, HSV-1 quantification, and pro-inflammatory cytokine levels.

Honey, used as an adjunct treatment, demonstrated benefits in combination with ACV, significantly improving pain, eating and drinking ability, and reducing the need for painkillers compared to ACV alone. Honey's anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and wound healing properties contribute to these effects. However, the cariogenic nature of honey should be considered, and the long-term consequences of its use in children require further evaluation.

In conclusion, while ACV remains a key therapeutic agent for PHGS, the identified studies emphasize the need for more research on effective and well-tolerated treatments, considering the challenges in prompt diagnosis and the potential complications associated with delayed intervention.

As previously mentioned, alleviating symptoms, particularly pain, is a primary objective of PHGS therapy. Bardellini et al. compared the efficacy of non-alcoholic chlorhexidine rinses alone and in combination with hyaluronic acid gel or Mucosyte® [19,21,22]. While all therapies demonstrated effectiveness, a significant improvement in pain scoring and lesion severity was observed with the combination of non-alcoholic chlorhexidine rinses and Mucosyte®. Mucosyte® is a solution composed of verbascoside, polyvinylpyrrolidone, and sodium hyaluronate with reparative action, forming a protective film on the oral mucosa.

Faden reported the use of a mixture of maalox and diphenhydramine, although lacking scientific evidence on its benefits [18,23]. Concerns were raised about the dose, method, and frequency of administration, considering the potential risks of sedation in infants with diphenhydramine ingestion and the association of viscous lidocaine ingestion with seizures. Surprisingly, ACV was relatively infrequently used in Faden's report [18,24].

This systematic review has certain limitations. Firstly, the lack of a standardized research protocol in the included studies hinders the comparison of results. The heterogeneity of outcomes among studies further limits comparisons. Secondly, caution in interpreting results is advised due to methodological limitations, incomplete data in one study (study 3), and the potential for bias in outcomes assessment. Thirdly, the clinical applicability of findings is limited to treating symptoms secondary to PHGS. Most proposed treatments consist of empiric regimens of symptomatic drugs, which are ineffective against viral replication. Regarding ACV-based therapy, commonly used as the primary drug for PHGS treatment, current evidence on its therapeutic benefits is limited, with only one out of the five included studies providing weak evidence of its effectiveness. Standardizing protocols through well-structured randomized clinical trials (RCTs) is crucial for ensuring consistency in PHGS therapy, reducing treatment variability, and achieving better outcomes. However, the rapid onset and remission of the disease pose challenges for conducting RCTs, as the diagnostic delay of approximately 72 hours decreases the effectiveness of antiviral drugs.

In conclusion, despite the high global prevalence of PHGS, the absence of consensus on therapeutic management underscores existing evidence gaps. The studies incorporated into this systematic review indicate that, among the various therapies reported in the scientific literature, there is insufficient evidence to favor one therapeutic approach over another. Moreover, the majority of included studies focus on alleviating patient discomfort rather than addressing viral shedding.

REFERENCES

1. Crimi S, Fiorillo L, Bianchi A et al (2019) Herpes virus, oral clinical signs and QoL: systematic review of recent data. *Viruses* 21 11(5):463
2. Balasubramaniam R, Kuperstein AS, Stoopler ET (2014) Update on oral herpes virus infections. *Dent Clin North Am* 58(2):265–280.
3. Whitley RJ, Roizman B (2001) Herpes simplex virus infections. *Lancet* (London, England) 357(9267):1513–1518.
4. Baron S (ed.) (1996) *Medical microbiology* (4th ed.). University of Texas Medical Branch at Galveston, Galveston
5. Khalifa C, Slim A, Maroua G, Sioud S, Hentati H, Selmi J (2022) Herpes simplex virus infection: management of primary oral lesions in children. *Clin Case Rep.* 10(8).
6. Kolokotronis A, Doumas S (2006) Herpes simplex virus infection, with particular reference to the progression and complications of primary herpetic gingivostomatitis. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 12(3):202–211.
7. Koyuncu OO, MacGibeny MA, Enquist LW (2018) Latent versus productive infection: the alpha herpesvirus switch. *Future Virol* 13(6):431–443.
8. Leuci S, Coppola N, Cantile T, Calabria E, Mihai LL, Mignogna MD (2022) Aseptic meningitis in oral medicine: exploring the key elements for a challenging diagnosis: a review of the literature and two case reports. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 19(7):3919.
9. Nasser M, Fedorowicz Z, Khoshnevisan MH, Shahiri Tabarestani M (2008) Acyclovir for treating primary herpetic gingivostomatitis. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* (4):CD006700.
10. Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM et al (2021) The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 372:n71. (Published 2021 Mar 29)
11. Abdel-Naby Awad OG, Hamad AH (2018) Honey can help in herpes simplex gingivostomatitis in children: prospective randomized double blind placebo controlled clinical trial. *Am J Otolaryngol* 39(6):759–763.
12. Bardellini E, Amadori F, Veneri F, Conti G, Paderno A, Majorana A (2022) Adolescents and primary herpetic gingivostomatitis: an Italian overview. *Ir J Med Sci* 191(2):801–805.
13. Vellappally S, Mahmoud MH, Alaqeel SM et al (2022) Efficacy of antimicrobial photodynamic therapy versus antiviral therapy in the treatment of herpetic gingivostomatitis among children: a randomized controlled clinical trial. *Photodiagnosis Photodyn Ther* 39:102895.
14. Majewska A, Mlynarczyk-Bonikowska B (2022) 40 years after the registration of acyclovir: do we need new anti-herpetic drugs? *Int J Mol Sci.* 23(7):3431. (Published 2022 Mar 22)
15. Wei YP, Yao LY, Wu YY et al (2021) Critical review of synthesis, toxicology and detection of acyclovir. *Molecules* 26(21):6566. (Published 2021 Oct 29)
16. Boitsaniuk SI, Levkiv MO, Fedoniuk LY, Kuzniak NB, Bambuliak AV (2022) Acute herpetic stomatitis: clinical manifestations, diagnostics and treatment strategies. *Wiad Lek* 75(1 pt 2):318–323
17. Traves KP, Love G, Studdiford JS (2019) Erythema multiforme: recognition and management. *Am Fam Physician* 100(2):82–88
18. Hafsi W, Badri T. Erythema Multiforme (2023) In: StatPearls [Internet]. StatPearls, Treasure Island

19. Celentano A, Tovar S, Yap T, Adamo D, Aria M, Mignogna MD (2015) Oral erythema multiforme: trends and clinical findings of a large retrospective European case series. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol* 120(6):707–716.
20. Sokumbi O, Wetter DA (2012) Clinical features, diagnosis, and treatment of erythema multiforme: a review for the practicing dermatologist. *Int J Dermatol* 51(8):889–902
21. Махкамова Ф.Т. и др. СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПОРАЖЕНИЙ СЛИЗИСТОЙ ОБОЛОЧКИ ПОЛОСТИ РТА //Форум молодых ученых. – 2017. – №. 5 (9). – С. 1348-1352.
22. Махкамова Ф. Т., Якубова Ф. Х. Изучение роли слюны в поддержании гомеостаза органов полости рта //Medicus. – 2019. – №. 6. – С. 68-71.
23. Нигматов Р. Н., Якубова Ф. Х., Юлдашева Н. Р. Избирательная пришлифовка преждевременно контрактирующих зубов химическим способом //Избирательная пришлифовка преждевременно контрактирующих зубов химическим способом //Stomatologiya. – 2024. – №. 1. – С. 23-25.
24. Нигматов Р.Н. и др. Особенности состояния полости рта и оказания ортопедической стоматологической помощи больным с психическим заболеванием //Stomatologiya. – 2024. – №. 1. – С. 29-32.